

ISic1235

Epitaph for a freedman, Ioulios Diadoumenos

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Largo di Chiesa di San Giovanni Gerosolimitano Di Malta

Coordinates

38.199072, 15.556499

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale
interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory A3557

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 25.5 cm

Width 38 cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Lines 1-4: 30-40 mm

Interlineation

Average interlineation: 15 mm

Text

1. Ἰούλιος Διαδου μενὸς · Ἰουλίου
3. Κουαδράτου · ἀπε
4. λεύθερος · (vac.undefined)

Apparatus

Text after I.Messina 30

Translation (en)

Iulius Diadoumenus, son of Iulius Quadratus, a freedman

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492839

EDCS 38200021

EDCS 39101600

PHI 140720

PHI 313662

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0408 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

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Cagnat, R., Toutain, J., Jouguet, P. 1906-1927. Inscriptiones Graecae ad res Romanas pertinentes. Paris. At 485

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